

THE ROLE OF DIHS IN FACILITATING THE DIGITAL TRANSITION. A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS: ROMANIA - EU

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Abstract

Purpose – The study maps the Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) in Romania (based on the European Union comparison) and identifies the main features of the Romanian DIH system.

Methodology/approach - Data was collected from secondary sources (Smart Specialization Platform – S3P). The comparative and descriptive analyses allowed the shaping of the Romanian DIHs profile.

Findings – The analyses indicated that Romania is below the EU average in terms of the established DIHs. Romanian DIHs offer services at regional level and do not cover all sectors and service categories delimited in S3P.

Research limitations/implications – The study provides representative conclusions only for Romania. However, based on the proposed methodological model, the analyzes can be extended to other EU countries.

Practical implications – The study results are useful both to SMEs in Romania (seeking support for digital transition in the post-pandemic period), but also to organizations that are interested in creating associative structures in the form of DIHs. For these, knowing the current profile of Romanian DIHs becomes essential, because it allows intervention on sectors and services not covered by existing hubs.

Originality/value – From the data known by the authors, until this date a complex analysis of all DIHs registered in Romania has not been performed. Therefore, the study fills the literature gap and contributes to a more advanced knowledge of Romania's situation compared to the EU.

Key words: digital innovation hubs, Romania, European Union.

Introduction

The Digital Europe Program, for the 2021-2027 period, aims to increase EU competitiveness by providing financial support for the development of key fields (artificial intelligence, high-performance computing, cyber security, advanced digital skills and digitalization of public administration and interoperability). The ultimate goal of the program is to ensure the digital transition and recovery of the European economy due to the COVID-19 pandemic crisis.

The main actors of the program are the Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), which have to facilitate the access of enterprises to new technologies, in a customized ecosystem through an adequate level of cyber security, which will facilitate digital innovation and economic development. DIHs serve both private and public sectors, facilitating access to innovative solutions. As legal entities, DIHs are created by an organization or group of organizations, that make their services available to SMEs and other entities. The offered services are: support services for digital transformation (which also allow testing and experimentation); support services for know-how transfer between entities/regions; support services for the development of key areas; services to provide the financial support needed to develop advanced digital skills.

The main objective of this study is to map Romanian DIHs and the EU DIHs, in order to identify and recover potential gaps. The main argument of the research is that, in the scientific literature, no studies have been identified that would allow the drawing of a Romanian DIHs profile. The study has a double utility. First, it directs Romanian SMEs to the DIHs that can best support them. Secondly, it provides

guidance to the new DIHs that will be set up and which are expected to cover sectors and provide services that are not yet provided.

Literature review

Scientific research on DIHs is at an early stage. The proof is the small number of researches published on this topic. For example, on the search date (July 5, 2022), the Web of Science platform records that in the last 5 years, 941 studies have been published, of which only 126 are assigned to the following categories: management (14), business (12), computer science information systems (12), computer science theory methods (11). Of the 126 studies, 91% are published since 2019. Most research focuses on case studies (Mauer, 2021; Rundel and Salemin, 2022, Barasti et al, 2022), or address topics of general interest, such as: the challenges and opportunities for DIHs development (Gernego et al, 2021; Georgescu et al, 2021); the services offered (Asplund et al, 2021); innovation strategies (Queiroz et al 2020); business models (Dalmarco et al, 2021) etc.

Other studies examine DIHs from the perspective of knowledge brokers (Crupi et al, 2020) or solution providers for solving social and environmental problems (Vrain et al, 2022). The Romanian researchers have published only five studies in the last 5 years. A study evaluates the extent to which the Romanian business environment has been prepared for the digital transition (Pinzaru et al, 2017). Another study analyzes the extent to which public services capitalize on digital technologies, focused on e-government services (Linearu et al, 2018). Lincaru et al (2019) analyzed the dynamics of the mechatronic field and brought into discussion the roles of the new associative structures. Grigorescu et al (2020) analyzed the interdependencies between the welfare of the population and the components of the digitalization trends.

Having this into consideration, an analysis of the Romanian DIHs profile has not yet been performed. Therefore, this study offers novelties in the existing scientific literature.

Methodology

The research methodology was based on descriptive and comparative analyzes on the DIHs profile in EU and Romania. Analyzing the UE perspective, the volume of the DIHs activity registered in Romania was compared. The analysis is based on secondary data, collected from the S3P (European Commission- EC, 2022). Although each DIH has its own virtual identity (through their own websites), the EU-managed platform provides - in a common organization - essential information about European DIHs.

To receive validation, DIHs must meet the following conditions: they are the result of a regional/national/European policy initiative; they are organized as non-profit entities; have a registered on-site headquarters and an updated website; provide support for SMEs in digital transformation.

When enrolling in the S3P, DIHs must provide the following information:

- contact details, legal representative, year of establishment and a brief description of the activity and its objectives;
- internal organization and financial information, such as turnover and number of employees;
- the identification category (fully operational, in preparation or potential DIHs from H2020);
- the geographical coverage provided (global, international, European, regional or national);
- funds accessed for funding: projects (such as Horizon 2020), European, national or regional funding, funding from clients, partners or members;
- the main partners and the technologies made available to customers;
- the market served, specifying the activity sectors and the technological readiness level (TRL); in the platform are 36 sectors defined and 9 levels of TRL;
- the annual number of clients, with details on entity size (start-ups, SMEs, large companies), area and field of activity (national or multinational, research, etc.);
- services offered- a DIH offers one or more services from the 16 predefined categories.

Based on these data, in this study we will focus on the EU DIHs and those registered in Romania.

Results and discussion

The analysis carried out for the 27 EU Member States indicated the following:

1. In the EU, 625 DIHs are registered in the S3P, with an average of 23 DIHs per Member State. Their distribution by country is not uniform. The countries with the highest number of registered DIHs are: Spain (90), Italy (73), Germany (65), France (54), Netherlands (46). The lowest number of DIHs are recorded in Malta (2), Cyprus, Luxembourg and Slovakia (5). Of the 625 DIHs, 375 are fully operational, 192 are in preparation and 58 are potential DIHs from H2020 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Structure of DIHs at EU level
Source: S3P, database processed by the authors

2. To accelerate the impact of DIHs and to support SMEs in implementing the digital technologies, EU has made available a set of tools and smart investment sources. The Horizon 2020 program aims to support research and development of communications and information technology. Thus, European DIHs network are supported to provide as many services as possible for the local SMEs. The extent to which DIHs have accessed these tools is shown in Figure 2. In the “fully operational” category, 78 DIHs - mostly from Spain (17), Italy (12), Germany (9) and France (7) - have benefited from H2020 support. In the “in preparation” category, 25 DIHs applied for projects in H2020, most of which were registered in Spain (4), Germany (4), Italy (3), Luxembourg (3), Sweden (3).

Figure 2. DIHs in H2020 projects
Source: S3P, database processed by the authors

3. The EU periodically launches calls and selects new DIHs to be part of the European network. At the time of this research, there were 316 DIHs candidate on the Smart Specialization Platform (S3P). Comparing the total number of registered DIHs at European level with the number of candidate DIHs, it shows that the states with the most registered DIHs also have the most candidate DIHs: Italy (45), Spain (40), Germany (33), France (17). The exception is Poland, which has 25 candidate DIHs, given that only 23 DIHs are registered in the S3P (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Candidate European DIHs
Source: S3P, database processed by the authors

The analysis carried out in Romania indicated the following:

1. In the S3P are registered 15 Romanian DIHs (Table 1 and Figure 4). Of the fully operational DIHs, most were established after 2014, with the exception of Wallachia eHub, which was established in 1991. A number of 12 DIHs provide services at the regional level, covering 6 of the 7 development regions (except the South-West Oltenia Region, in which no DIH is listed).

Table 1. Romanian DIHs

No	DIHs name	Established Year	Fully operational	In preparation	DIHs in H2020 projects	Geographical Range
1	BEIA DIH	2014	x			regional
2	CiTyInnoHub	2019		x		regional
3	Cluj IT Cluster	2012		x		regional
4	Danube Digital Innovation Hub	2020	x			regional
5	Digital Innovation Hub for Society (DIH4S)	2017	x			regional
6	Digital Innovation SMART eHUB	N/A	x			regional
7	DIH West Region Romania	2019		x		regional
8	Futures of Innovation and Technology	2020	x			regional
9	North-East Romania - Digital Innovation Zone	2017	x			regional
10	RO Tech Nation DIH	2020	x			regional
11	Sibiu Smart Systems	2015	x			regional
12	Transilvania Digital Innovation Hub - DIH	2017	x			regional
13	Universitatea de Vest of Timisoara	N/A			x	
14	Universitatea Lucian Blaga of Sibiu	N/A			x	
15	Wallachia eHub	1991	x			regional

Source: database processed by the authors from S3P

Figure 4. Romanian DIHs
Source: S3P, database processed by the authors

2. The analysis of the turnover performed by the Romanian DIHs indicated the following results: Digital Innovation Zone (North-East Romania DIH) registered a turnover of +5 million euro; BEIA DIH and Wallachia eHub had a turnover between 1 - 5 million euro; Digital Innovation SMART eHUB declared a turnover between 0.25 - 0.50 million euro; the other DIHs declared a turnover of less than 0.25 million euro.

3. Regarding the annual number of customers, 4 DIHs stated that they have more than 50 customers (BEIA DIH; Digital Innovation SMART eHUB; DIH West Region Romania; Transilvania Digital Innovation Hub - Transilvania DIH; Wallachia eHub). The other DIHs had annually between 0-5 customers (Sibiu Smart Systems), 6-10 (CiTyInnoHub, North-East Romania DIH - "Digital Innovation Zone"), 11-25 (Danube Digital Innovation Hub, Digital Innovation Hub for Society) and 26-50 customers for Cluj IT Cluster, Futures of Innovation and Technology Digital Innovation Hub, RO Tech Nation DIH.

4. The sector analysis in which DIHs offer services, indicated that education, public administration and agriculture are the best covered sectors. The services covering these sectors are provided by 10-12 DIHs (Figure 5). It is highlighted that 13 sectors are not offered by the Romanian DIHs: aeronautics and space; consumer goods/products; cultural and creative industries; defense and security; environment; chemical manufacturing; chemical products and man-made fibers; manufacture of coke; refined petroleum products and nuclear fuel; manufacture of other non-metallic miner products; pulp, paper and paper products manufacturing; publishing and printing, mining and quarrying, mobility (including automotive); professional, scientific and technical activities; telecommunications; information and communication.

5. According to H2020, 9 levels of TRL are defined: TRL1 - Basic principles observed and reported; TRL2 - Technology concept and / or application formulated; TRL3 - Analytical and experimental critical function and / or characteristic proof of concept; TRL4 - Component and / or breadboard validation in laboratory environment; TRL5 - Component and / or breadboard validation in relevant environment; TRL6 - System / subsystem model or prototype demonstration in a relevant environment; TRL7 - System prototype demonstration in an operational environment; TRL8 - Actual system completed and qualified through test and demonstration; TRL9 - Actual system proven through successful mission operations. Of the 13 Romanian DIHs, only 3 (CiTyInnoHub, Digital Innovation SMART eHUB, Wallachia eHub) cover the 9 TRL levels. Danube Digital Innovation Hub offers services only for the TRL5 level (Table 2).

6. According to the EU, 16 services categories offered by DIHs are defined: access to funding and investor readiness services (Af&i); awareness creation (Ac); collaborative researches (Cr); commercial infrastructure (Ci); concept validation and prototyping (Cvp); digital maturity assessment (Dma); ecosystem building, scouting, brokerage, networking (Ec); education and skills development (Ed); incubator / accelerator support (Is); market intelligence (Mi); mentoring (M); Other (O); pre-competitive series production (PcS); testing and validation (TV); visioning and strategy development for businesses (VSdB); voice of the customer, product consortia (Vc). The analysis of the Romanian DIHs shows that they cover most of the previously mentioned services. The largest coverage on services is Digital Innovation SMART eHUB and Futures of Innovation and Technology Digital Innovation Hub, which offers 13 (respectively, 12) of the 16 service categories (Table 3).

Figure 5. Sectors covered by the Romanian DIHs Source: S3P, database processed by the authors

Table 2. TRL - Romanian DIHs

DIHs name	TRL1	TRL2	TRL3	TRL4	TRL5	TRL6	TRL7	TRL8	TRL9
BEIA DIH				x	x	x	x	x	x
CiTyInnoHub	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Cluj IT Cluster					x	x	x	x	x
Danube Digital Innovation Hub					x				
Digital Innovation Hub for Society (DIH4S)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		
Digital Innovation SMART eHUB	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
DIH West Region Romania		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Futures of Innovation and Technology					x	x	x	x	x
North-East Romania - Digital Innovation Zone	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		
RO Tech Nation DIH	x	x	x	x	x	x			
Sibiu Smart Systems		x	x	x	x				
Transilvania Digital Innovation Hub - DIH	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Universitatea de Vest of Timisoara									
Universitatea Lucian Blaga of Sibiu									
Wallachia eHub	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

Source: S3P, database processed by the authors

The data in table 3 also indicates that the services associated with the commercial infrastructure are not covered by the Romanian DIHs, while the pre-competitive series production, voice of the customer services, the product consortium services have poor coverage.

Conclusions

After the review of the scientific literature - that revealed the lack of knowledge regarding the particularities of the Romanian DIHs - the research, conducted by the authors, focused on mapping the DIHs in the EU and Romania.

Table 3. Services provided by Romanian DIHs

DIHs name	Services															
	Af&i	Ac	Cr	Ci	Cvp	Dma	Ec	Ed	Is	Mi	M	O	PcS	TV	VSbD	Vc
BEIA DIH	x	x	x				x	x	x	x	x			x	x	x
CiTylInnoHub	x	x				x	x	x	x		x			x	x	
Cluj IT Cluster	x		x		x		x	x			x			x	x	
Danube Digital Innovation Hub		x	x					x	x		x			x		
Digital Innovation Hub for Society	x	x	x		x	x	x	x							x	
Digital Innovation SMART eHUB	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	x	x
DIH West Region Romania		x	x			x	x	x			x				x	
Futures of Innov. and Technol.	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x		x		x	x	x	
North-East Romania – DI Zone		x	x		x		x	x	x		x			x	x	
RO Tech Nation DIH		x	x		x		x	x	x		x			x	x	
Sibiu Smart Systems		x	x		x		x	x				x		x		
Transilvania DIH		x	x		x		x	x	x			x		x		
Univ. de Vest of Timisoara																
Univ. Lucian Blaga of Sibiu																
Wallachia eHub	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x				x	

Source: S3P, database processed by the authors

The comparative analysis reported the following:

- the number of DIHs registered in Romania (15) is well below the EU average (23); this is a weak point for Romania; in other words, the Romanian business environment does not have the same support (as EU SMEs) to facilitate their digital transition;
- in EU, the fully operational DIHs are 60% of the total DIHs; in Romania, fully operational DIHs represent 67% of the total, which is a favorable aspect;
- only two Romanian DIHs managed to access funds from H2020; the EU average is 4 DIHs per EU member state; in order to increase the access to H2020 funding and to provide more services to the business environment, Romanian DIHs must pay attention to the eligibility criteria established for accessing funds;
- Romania has 12 candidate DIHs for European recognition, which places it very close to the EU average; strengthening the DIHs infrastructure creates access to consistent support for SMEs in the digital transition.

The analysis at the Romanian DIHs allowed the formulation of the following conclusions:

- out of the 15 Romanian DIHs, 10 are fully operational, 3 are in preparation and 2 are potential DIHs from H2020;
- these DIHs cover only 6 of the 7 development regions;
- only 1 DIH has a turnover of more than 5 million euro; this DIH has in its portfolio only 9 of the 16 possible services; other DIHs, which provide more services, had lower turnovers; the new DIHs that will be registered in Romania must keep in mind that the number of services they offer is not a guarantee of success; more important is the adequacy of the portfolio to the needs of customers (mostly SMEs);
- only four DIHs have more than 50 customers per year; these do not include the DIH with the highest turnover, which stated that it has between 11 and 25 customers per year;
- existing DIHs mainly cover three sectors: education, public administration and agriculture; 20 sectors are partially covered; 13 sectors remain uncovered; in order to facilitate the digital transition for SMEs in all sectors, the new DIHs to be registered in Romania must take these aspects into account;

- only 3 Romanian DIHs have all 9 TRL stages; in order to identify new market sectors, the new Romanian DIHs must adjust their offer taking into account the needs of SMEs, but also the technological maturity of existing DIHs.

Limitations and future research

The present study was based on a quantitative analysis that used secondary data. In future research we have in mind a qualitative analysis (based on primary data) that would allow the creation of a complete profile of the Romanian DIHs from the perspective of the legal representatives of these business associative structures.

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